

A WOMAN IN ERKIN AZAM'S "PAKANA'S LOVER'S HEART"

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ABSTRACT

This article presents general thoughts, theories, definitions about the concept. At the same time, the two fields directly related to the concept are cognitive linguistics and linguistic culture, and how these two fields are related to the concept, and brief information about the use of the concept of woman in other languages, in particular, in French, as well as in Uzbek, woman the application of the concept, in particular, in Erkin Azam's work "Pakana's Lover's Heart", social, and artistic significance of this concept are attached, and thoughts about the concept of a woman, its definition and the general the conclusions are summarized.

It is known that linguistics came to its current state step by step through many stages. Language is the most important communication tool, and the development of this tool began with the appearance of mankind on earth. It is such a process that its development takes place naturally by itself. The result of this development will be perfected as the number of people on earth increases and with the passage of time. It is also worth noting that amazing progress has been made in language and linguistics, and many abstract secrets of the language have been revealed. But the fact that science has no boundaries is also reflected in linguistics.

In particular, the concept concept in cognitive linguistics and linguistic culture is one of the new directions of linguistics.

Different scholars have expressed different opinions about the concept. If we look at the history, the term concept has been used since 90s of the 20th century. V. A. Askaldov, one of the linguists who the conducted research on the concept, said that the concept: "It is a unit that reflects the process of thinking about one type or another concept."

N.D. Aryutanova: "It is a practical concept in philosophy, it reflects factors such as religion, ideology, images of folk art, and relationships between thinking. It contains a cultural layer that 2 establishes the connection between man and the world. show?2

And D.S. Lichasheva in the scientific work "Konceptosfera russkogo yazyka" "with the dictionary meaning of the word concept, a person's national views defined as a product of the thinking process that is formed as a result of the interaction.

The word concept is directly related to cognitive linguistics and linguistic culture, linguistic culture. But there are differences in the definition of the term yes concept in the two

fields. Cognitive linguistics is still a new science. "Cognize" is derived from the word "to know", "to understand". application and transmission is a deep scientific research in connection with thinking as a reflection of the structure of the language system in the human brain". Linguistics studies the reflection of knowledge in language, i.e. its verbalization⁵.

Linguistics also grew rapidly towards the end of the 20th century. Linguistics is a general science between cultural studies and linguistics. Researches the interaction and relationship between language and culture and the manifestation of this relationship in language. One of the main categories for these two areas is concept. The term concept is defined in the dictionary of cognitive terms as "Concept is a concept that serves to reflect mental and psychic resources in our thinking in human knowledge and skills" ⁶. In linguistic culture, the interpretation of the concept is slightly different. Yu. A. Stepanov and A.S. Askaldov's opinions about the concept are similar. That is, according to Askaldov, "Concept is one of the elements of culture, it is a form formed in human thinking. In the same way, culture penetrates into the mental world of a person ⁷. researched, but also shows that they include the excitement, value, national image and connotation that they feel, and that value and spirituality are at the center of the concept. He mentioned in his thoughts that he should pay attention to research, that value is based on culture.

Therefore, the concept is a language unit that is actively used in both linguistic culture and cognitive linguistics. We can say that the at the time, as well as the most complete set of thoughts that arise as a result of the union of knowledge and cultural values, culture and knowledge, art., there will be no mistake. If we take the "woman concept is the highest level of understanding, the most beautiful, even negative concept" as an example, this concept will be renewed by the peoples of the whole world, linguistics, society, and its members. The concept of woman, as well as language, cultural aspects and social aspects are perfected in many languages, in French, too, there are continuous movements with different negative and positive sides. For example, in French, a woman is the age of puberty, marriageable age, and it is undoubtedly the most the study and research processes. As the concept of woman is used in translated as "Femme" (fam). The term woman is often associated with commonly used expression for women in the French language.

l'une Femme des femmas - women synonyms of the lexical unit Femme (file) -girl, mademoiselle demoiselle dame - beauty, amie - female friend, mere- mother, mitress - mistress, maman matron, babonne-wife, o' gay mother-pape, mattet (beloved) netet-beautiful girl, beloved girl.

Common definitions for a woman: a kind woman - bonne; wife, spouse-epoux, housewife - femme au fayer ⁸ Woman in French concept is used in a wide sense and its meaning is expanding.

The concept of woman is a new concept in the Uzbek language, and this type of concept is being researched. In particular, Professor Shahriyor Safarov's work "Cognitive Linguistics contains very beautiful examples of the concept of woman.

Characteristics of a woman	Examples
Respect the values of life a woman who does	Always puts her family first, loving, kind, cook,

	patient, true friend, forgiving moderate, honest, honest, sincere, sweet, soft-spoken. thrifty
Smart	Thoughtful, self-confident, intelligent, intelligent, attentive, in front of strangers restrained, cultured, understanding, national values respectable
Dream	Honorable, faithful, virtuous religiously and secularly educated, conscientious, exemplary chaste, enlightened
External beauty	Feminine, tenacious, elegant ambitious
Brave	Hard-working, strong enterprising, patient enthusiastic

So, if we say that the concept of woman is a collection of concepts that is widely and widely used in any language and nation and never ceases to be studied, then we are correct. Also, the concept of "woman" is widely used in the works of writers, and this type of concept has been inspiring the representatives of the field of art for a long time. In particular, in the works of Erkin A'zam, the concept of woman is beautifully interpreted in various aspects.

Erkin Azam was born on August 10, 1950 in Boysun district of (1972-1976), the head of the department at the "Guliston" magazine (1981-1986), and Surkhandarya region. He studied at the current Faculty of Journalism of Tashkent State University. He worked as an editor at the Radio of Uzbekistan the head of the publishing house of many volumes at the literary and art publishing house named after Gafur Ghulom. The story "Ilk Inson", written during the student years of the writer, was published in the regional newspaper. A number of his stories were published, such as "Atoi's birthday", "Pakana's love heart", "The man who sleeps late", "The answer", "Heaven is the rule", "Shajara", "The dream of the cleaning lady", "House the owner", "The lonely boat or the dream of a madman plays were staged in the cinemas of our country.

[http://Saviya.uz.biography/Erkin Azam 1950](http://Saviya.uz.biography/Erkin%20Azam%201950)

Erkin A'zam's "Pakana's Heart in Love" tells the and the pain of the lover's heart, and before falling in love. The obsession with beauty focuses on girls who are older than him or taller than story of the main character himself and his dream, the height growth descriptions of girls in his stories about girls and the hymns of Safsar, whom he was in love with, can be many examples of the concept of a woman. At the beginning of the story, our hero Pakana's him. it is shown that the reef is given. In another place, the word beautiful imaginary figure says that a woman is a mysterious being, and every representative of the male race recreates a woman in his mind. In this work of the writer, it is described not only in praise but also in a negative way. In particular, the phrase "ul bewafa" is a literary word that embodies the image of a woman who betrayed 7 her husband or abandoned her husband and left him. This word is often used in artistic, literary, and poetic works. Again, he describes Pakana's old lover

Aziza with beautiful, graceful, charming words. Lakma used many images to describe the negative aspects as well. In this a girl, but the qualities and definitions given to a woman expand throughout the work. For example, in the work, we got concepts that are used not only for a woman, but for a woman. For example, the there are inappropriate thoughts about a woman. These definitions are work, a woman is generally called a woman, a young woman, a wife, fact that all the negative concepts given to a woman: uglier, poorer, infertile, divorced, angry, nervous, etc., sometimes indicate that sometimes reflected in opinions about appearance.

Words that describe the positive aspects of a woman only in terms of her appearance: beautiful, luscious-haired, charming, attractive, graceful, handsome, possessive, graceful, handsome, handsome, graceful, charming are external. it shows that the artistic and literary side of the view has been opened.

In the work, the definitions of the inner world of a woman are as follows: soulful, kind, innocent, beautiful, beautiful lady, virgin, nazanin, hyacinth-haired, mysterious angel, beloved, these words are listed as the aesthetic characteristics of a woman at the artistic level. In addition, the work contains such comparisons that it is impossible not to attach it:

MASHUQA - This is an image of a mysterious woman in love, and this word occupies a central place in many works, poems, ghazals, and it deserves to be called a very beautiful and passionate aesthetic image.

A GULTAJI OF THE PERIOD - is a description of a woman who is loved by everyone and can attract everyone to her opinion.

IMMUNE BUDDLE - this definition is said about girls who are beautiful, still innocent, and whose looks show purity.

PARIVASH BIR RUKSOR- this simile is mainly used to draw a picture of a woman aesthetically with words. Even with this word, it is possible to hint that a woman is a divine being, of course, in a figurative sense.

SAHIBJAMOL FRIENDS WITH GAMZA - this definition means that the flirtations of a beautiful woman who is in love with her lover are depicted in words.

A PEOPLE OF BEAUTIFUL PEOPLE is a picture of a group of beautiful women or girls gathered at a party or gathering.

We can give many more of these definitions. The most important thing is that these words, definitions, and concepts can be a set of important tools for expanding the concept of women.

At the end of the article, we can make the following conclusion: the concept concept is very comprehensive, this term does not stop developing and expanding, and knowledge about it can be one of the main factors in reaching the perfect level of people's culture and knowledge.

"Women's concept" is one of the types of concepts that enhance aesthetics, this type of concept never ceases to be researched and expanded. Because a woman is a creature that makes life colorful, she is a delicate creature that changes. Nature, a society of men, draws inspiration from them. He is an inspiration. If knowledge, concepts, understandings, research and development about women stop, life will literally stop, even if it does not stop, the interest in life will disappear. In the works of Erkin A'zam, the concept of woman has acquired

a unique appeal in terms of style and art. It is impossible not to emphasize that the presence of the concept of women in the works of this writer, who is famous for his works in which views of freedom are the main focus, is surprising. So, in any case, in any work, if one or more words about a woman are absent, a synonym concept is given to her. This becomes a concept. "Women's concept" does not stop developing.

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